

IMPLEMENTATION OF ENERGY EFFICIENT CLUSTERED CHAIN BASED POWER TRACKING ROUTING PROTOCOL (EECCPTR) IN WSN

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Abstract:

Cluster based routing have been successful to enhance the lifetime of the sensor network and also reduced the overall cost of communication. Conventional clustering protocols classifies the sensor network into a number of clusters and every cluster has a cluster head. The sensor nodes routinely sends their received data to their respective CHs and the CHs functions to aggregate data and then transmit this accumulated data to the BS. Thus CHs drains energy more quickly than other nodes in the clusters, reducing the lifetime of the networks. Several clustering protocols like LEACH rotates the cluster heads in order to maintain the energy of all the nodes. But it suffers from clustering overhead. Static clustering avoids the overhead of dynamic clustering. But these clusters do not allow new nodes to join the clusters and thus the nodes performance is not affected by nodes dying. To avoid this chain based routing protocols were proposed. PEGASIS is a chain based protocol but it suffers from transmission delays due to long links. In order to avoid this we proposed Energy Efficient Clustered Chain Based Power tracking Routing Protocol (EECCPTR) For Wireless Sensor Networks. The main objective of this protocol is to enhance the lifetime of the network and reduce the communication cost by homogeneously distributing the energy load among associated sensor nodes.

Keywords: Cluster, enhance, energy, lifetime, overhead, network

1) Introduction

Most Wireless sensor network (WSN) is a modern necessity. It has manifold benefits in everyday life. It is an integral part of modern day technology and is extensively used in personal, commercial and industrial areas viz. environmental monitoring and assessment, current healthcare will be almost crippled without it, process monitoring and surveillance systems. WSN

comprises of subunits which are small devices known as nodes. Nodes refer to transceiver, CPU, battery and memory. WSN functioning depends on several parameters like network's lifetime, network topology, weather conditions at a given time and place, node type and zone around a specific sink node. In this project we have focused on lifetime of WSN. WSN's lifetime depends upon few factors ie how much is the battery life, the amount of energy consumption by nodes, also number of packets lost. All of these factors are manageable using different such as that of Network coding, duty cycle management, topology management, routing the algorithms. Here we have made an effort to implement duty cycle management approach and sparingly introduced different approaches other than duty cycle which includes network coding and cluster head selection.

I. WSN NETWORK TECHNIQUES

This specific network coding technique facilitates receiving of original data at target node. This is done with the help of the intermediate node which encodes the data and then transfer it to the next node thereby ensuring original packet are received and decoded at end node. This idea of network coding ensures authentic & reliable transfer of data that to at a better packet delivery ratio. When we ignore the unwanted data packets energy consumption reduces significantly and it also enhances the lifetime of WSN. The data transferred utilizing routing algorithm is the efficient way of transmission.

There are a number of routing algorithms available, but the cluster head selection algorithm is comparatively better efficient. Cluster head selection method works in a way that a single node is selected from a cluster, this node serves as a cluster head. It collects data from adjacent node and relay them to the base station. The cluster head is nominated considering residual energy and lowest mobility factor. This approach thus provides better routing algorithm. A better routing for the purpose of communication then serves to facilitate lifetime optimization. In our current project we have applied an eclectic approach by incorporating cluster head selection algorithm, duty cycle management and the network coding approach in unison for better results.

Fig: Snapshot showing Cluster Node formation in WSN

Battery serves as the core energy source in WSNs and there is a limit to battery supplied power. It becomes extremely difficult or say impossible to replace or recharge once the sensor nodes are installed at a site. In which case it is wise to consume the battery power efficiently. Considering this as a significant concerns different energy efficient protocols have been proposed from time to time.

II. PROBLEM STATED

We have used First order radio model. Assumptions of model discussed here are as follows.

3.1 Assumptions

- Sensor nodes are stationary after installed and BS is located at far location from the sensing field.
- All concerned sensor nodes have same initial energy ie there is homogeneity in sensor nodes.
- Energy requirement for transmitting & receiving a message is the same ie radio channel both ways is symmetric
- All the sensor nodes have insight of their location and energy.

The energy model described previously is being used for communication. The calculation of energy dissipation, Transmission Energy required to convey 1 bit of data over coldness d is done using the following formula :

$$E_{Tx}(l, d) = \begin{cases} lE_{elec} + l \epsilon_{fs} d^2, d < d_0 \\ lE_{elec} + l \epsilon_{amp} d^4, d \geq d_0 \end{cases} \dots\dots\dots (3.1)$$

To receive similar message energy required will be:

$$E_{Rx}(l) = lE_{elec} \dots\dots\dots (3.2)$$

Where E_{elec} refers to energy which is dissipated to run the transmitter amplifier and $\epsilon_{fs} d^2$ or $\epsilon_{amp} d^4$ is the amplifier energy, depends upon acceptable bit-error rate.

On careful analysis of equation it can be seen that in receiving information a lot of energy is consumed. Thus the number of transmission and receiving should be reduced, in order to maximize the energy usage.

III. PROPOSED APPROACH

Energy Efficient Clustered Chain Based Power Tracking Routing Protocol (EECCPTR)

In this project work we are suggesting an Energy Efficient Clustered Chain Based Power Tracking Routing Protocol (EECCPTR) for WSNs in order to increase system lifetime and bring down the message cost. The functioning of recommended protocol is divided into rounds. Each of these rounds consists of following phases:

- a. Clustering Phase.
- b. Chain Formation Phase.
- c. Data Transmission Phase.

Due to reduction of clustering overhead, clustering is not performed in each rounding in our proposed protocol. The sensor nodes utilize residual energy of nodes to nominate a CH for the next round instead BS station selecting the CHs.

3.4. a Clustering Phase

Clustering phase consists of two stages which are as follows:

- Cluster Head Selection.
- Cluster Formation.

Cluster Head Selection

In proposed model, every individual node maintains an adjacent neighbouring table to store the information concerning their neighbours. Every concerned node uses GPS (Global Positioning System) to be aware of its residual energy and geographical location with. Each node is capable of broadcasting its information to all the other nodes falling in their radio range using CSMA MAC protocol. Each node which is a hop away in the radio range “r” of the broadcasting node are neighbours of that node. Each node receives the information message in the radio range and updates its neighbourhood table. Then each node estimates its distance from its neighbour nodes and also they calculates their weights by following formula:

$$W_i = RE_i \times \sum_{j=1}^n \frac{1}{d^2(v_i, v_j)} \dots\dots\dots (3.3)$$

In the above equation

W_i is the weight of node i and

$d(v_i, v_j)$ is the distance between

Node “i” and node “j” .Now each node broadcasts its weight in the radio range r and the node which has the highest weight among all its neighbours in the radio range r is selected as Cluster Head(CH).

Cluster Formation

Once the cluster heads are selected, these broadcasts an advertisement message, which consists of the nodes ID and header which makes it stand out from other messages. CHs use non

persistent CSMA MAC protocol to broadcast these messages. The nodes select their CH depending upon the Received Signal Strength Information (RSSI). Now the node sends the join request message to the chosen CH. The add request message carries the nodes ID & CHs ID to which the node wants to join. The node utilizes non persistent Carrier Sense Multiple Access (CSMA) MAC protocol to send the add request message to the CHs.

The clustering phase has high overhead and thus it is not performed in every round. If a node within the cluster dies then the CH informs the BS that the sensors should not perform clustering in the beginning of the next round. Otherwise sensors nodes select the new CHs base on the Residual energy of the nodes.

3.4.2 Chain Formation Phase

This round consist of following stages:

1. Chain Formation Among CHs.
2. Chain Formation Within Clusters.

Chain Formation Among CHs

The cluster heads transmits their geographical location and Residual energy to the base station. Thereafter base station creates a chain of all the cluster heads based on the received information from various sources. Base station then transmits this compiled information to the cluster heads. The base station uses greedy algorithm to form the chain among concerned cluster heads. Chain formation is such that. It starts from the furthest node to the nearest node from the base station and nearer node to the base station has the better opportunity to become the leader of the cluster heads in the chain.

IV. RESULT ANALYSIS

Evaluation of the performance of EECCPTR protocol is done by simulation. For simulation we used MATALAB and tested our protocols performance with PEGASIS and LEACH.

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Fig: Simulation Snapshot showing the sync point, its parameters and its track.

Fig: Simulator Showing data Path in WSN.

For the purpose of performance evaluation following parameters were taken into account:

- Energy consumption
- Load balancing
- Network Throughout

4.5 Simulation Setup

The size of network is taken as 100m X 100m. The number of nodes are 100 which are scattered randomly in the sensor field. BS is located at (50,170). Parameters of our simulation are as follows:

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Parameters	Values
Network Size	(0,0) to (100,100)
Number of nodes	100
Base Station Location	(50,175)
Cluster Radius r	20 m
Initial Energy Of Nodes	0.3J
Data Packet Size	500 Bytes
Broadcast Packet Size	25 Bytes
E_{elec}	50nJ/bit
ϵ_{fs}	100pJ/bit/m ²
ϵ_{amp}	0.0013pJ/bit/m ²
d_0	87.7 m
E_{DA}	5 nJ/bit/signal

Fig: Simulation Parameter

Fig: Simulation Graphs Showing residual energy in nodes, energy consumption, and energy saved.

V. Conclusion and Future Work

In this paper we proposed Energy Efficient Clustered Chain Based Power Tracking Routing protocol(EECCPTR) which maximizes the network lifetime and balances the energy consumption among the sensor nodes of the network. EECCPAR organises the whole network into clusters and selects cluster heads. Then it constructs chain within the clusters so that each node transmitt data to its next neighbor and receive data from its previous neighbor. In this protocol we also construct chain among cluster heads. Thus data was sent to the BS through the chain. Thus it helps nodes to transmitt data to a smaller distance and thus increases the lifetime of the network. In this protocol we doesn't forms clusters in each round. But in LEACH protocol, in each round clustering is done. Thus it(LEACH) su_ers from clustering overhead.Simulation results show that EECCPAR performs better than PEGASIS protocol in terms of Network Throughput, Load Balancing and number of data message transmitted to the BS. It Performs Better than other protocols like LEACH,since in our protocol clustering is not done in each round but in LEACH it is done in each round. In our protocol we also consider time critical data, which is not considered in other routing protocols. Time critical data should reach the destination quickly without much delay. For this we have introduce the concept of MAX threshold.

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